

Investigating the Impact of Benzydamine Gargling on Post- Operative Throat Discomfort

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Abstract:

Background: General anaesthesia with endotracheal intubation often results in postoperative sore throat, cough and hoarseness of voice. Benzydamine hydrochloride is a topical NSAID with analgesic, local anaesthetic, anti-inflammatory properties. We studied the effect of benzydamine hydrochloride gargling on the incidence and severity of sore throat, cough and hoarseness of voice in patients undergoing elective middle ear surgery under general anaesthesia with endotracheal intubation.

Methods: All the patients after explaining the procedure. 120 patients of either gender scheduled for elective middle ear surgeries under general anaesthesia with endotracheal intubation, who fulfilled the inclusion and exclusion criteria were included. Patients were randomized into two groups -Benzydamine hydrochloride group and control group using sealed envelope method. Patients in Benzydamine hydrochloride group were gargled 0.15% of 20ml benzydamine hydrochloride solution and control group patients gargled 20ml of 0.9% saline for 30secs, 5mins before intubation. After surgery and tracheal extubation, the incidence and severity of postoperative sore throat, cough, hoarseness of voice and any complications were assessed at 0, 2, 4, 6 and 24 hours.

Conclusion: Preoperative benzydamine hydrochloride oral gargle reduces the incidence and severity of sore throat, cough and hoarseness in patients who underwent elective middle ear surgery under general anaesthesia with endotracheal intubation.

Keywords: Sore Throat, Hoarseness, Benzydamine Hydrochloride.

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Introduction

Postoperative sore throat (POST) is a common minor complication after general anaesthesia (GA) with tracheal intubation and laryngeal mask airway (LMA) insertion occurring in 30 to 65% of patients. [1] It leads to patient dissatisfaction, physical discomfort and increased duration of hospital stay. [2,3] The causes of POST is due to several reasons which includes local inflammation of airway, [4] large size of the tracheal tube, 5 increased duration of surgery, [6] movement of tracheal tube and cuff during position change, airway damage during intubation, [7] and prone position. [8] It can be accompanied by cough, laryngitis, tracheitis, dysphagia or hoarseness. Modern anaesthesia is safe, versatile, and indispensable to the patient. Providing quality assurance of anaesthesia is important in improving the postoperative outcome of the patients. Therefore, efforts to decrease the anaesthesia related postoperative complications like postoperative nausea-vomiting and sore throat, including postoperative pain, are going on. [9] It is well recognized that prolonged intubation can have serious consequences, but it is less well recognized that uneventful intubation for routine surgical

procedures can also cause pathological changes that may provide an organic basis for patients' postoperative throat symptoms. Although in most cases it will resolve spontaneously, prevention focused on reducing its frequency and severity are recommended to better patient satisfaction and quality of postoperative care. [10] Numerous non-pharmacological and pharmacological measures have been used for attenuating POST with variable success. Among the non-pharmacological methods, smaller sized tracheal tubes, careful airway instrumentation, minimizing the number of laryngoscopy attempts, intubation after the full relaxation of the larynx, gentle oropharyngeal suctioning, filling the cuff with an anaesthetic gas mixture, minimizing intracuff pressures. This study was designed to compare the effect of Benzydamine oral gargling before surgery in patients who underwent ear surgeries under GA with endotracheal intubation. [11]

Objectives

To compare the effect of gargling of 0.15% Benzydamine hydrochloride solution for 30

seconds, five minutes before endotracheal intubation on postoperative sore throat, cough and hoarseness of voice in patients operated under general anaesthesia with endotracheal intubation for middle ear surgeries.

Materials and Methods

This prospective randomized study was conducted at Bhagwan Mahavir Institute of Medical Sciences Pawapuri, Nawada. Study Period May 2022 to may 2024. Patients scheduled for elective middle ear surgeries under general anaesthesia with endotracheal, A total of 120 patients (60 patients in each group) with below mentioned inclusion and exclusion criteria were enrolled for the study. Study design: A prospective randomized placebo controlled double blind study

Inclusion Criteria:

1. American Society of Anaesthesiologists (ASA) class 1-11
2. Age 20-60 years of either sex
3. Elective middle ear surgical procedures under general anaesthesia with oraltracheal intubation
4. Duration of surgery <4hrs

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Patients with history of preoperative sore throat
2. More than one attempt at intubation
3. Mallampati grade >2
4. Known smoker/allergies to BH
5. Patients on treatment with NSAIDs
6. Morbidly obese (BMI >35)

Written informed consent was taken from all the patients after explaining the procedure. 120 patients of either gender scheduled for elective middle ear surgeries who fulfilled the inclusion and exclusion criteria were included in the study. A thorough preoperative evaluation was done for all the patients on the previous day of surgery and were explained about the procedure. All patients were kept nil per oral for 8 hrs for solid foods and 4 hrs for clear fluids. On the day of surgery, after arrival to the

operation theatre, the patients were shifted to anaesthesia preparation room. Patients were randomized into two groups namely BH group (intervention group) and control group using sealed envelope method. Patients in BH group received oral gargle of 20 ml of 0.15% Benzydamine solution for 30 seconds. Patients in control group received oral gargle of 20 ml of 0.9% saline for 30 seconds. The solutions were prepared by a pharmacist in our pharmacy department so that the different solutions had the same external appearance. After 5 minutes of gargle, patients were shifted to operation table. 18G IV cannula was secured in left upper arm and Ringer's Lactate was started. ECG, NIBP, SpO2 monitors were connected and baseline readings were noted.

Results

A sample size of 55 patients was calculated considering a decreased incidence of POST from 40% to 20% with a power of 90% and a significance level of 0.05. To compensate for potential dropouts, we enrolled 60 patients in each group. A total of 120 Patients were enrolled in the study The data was analysed in using STATA 12.0 and SPSS 20.0 software. Continuous variables like age, weight, height, body mass index, and duration were reported as mean (SD). Categorical variables such as gender, type of surgery, ASA status, smoking, blood stain, postoperative parameters (sore throat, cough and hoarseness of voice), groups (intervention and control group) and side effects (nausea, vomiting, local tingling or numbness of the throat and mouth and dry mouth) were reported as proportions. The association between continuous variables and the groups (intervention and control) were assessed using unpaired t test and the association between categorical variable and groups were assessed using Chi Square test or Fisher's exact test based on the cell values. The difference between overall presence of postoperative parameters (sore throat, cough and hoarseness of voice), and side effects (nausea, vomiting, local tingling or numbness of the throat and mouth and dry mouth) between groups were assessed using difference between proportions test. p value of <0.05 was considered for statistical significance.

Table 1: Age distribution

Age in years	Intervention group (Benzydamine) N (%)	Control group (Normal Saline) N (%)	p value
Mean (SD)	31.1 (7.8)	32.1 (8.1)	0.465*

Un paired t test

The number of male and female participants in intervention (benzydamine) group are 29 (48.3%) and 31 (51.7%) respectively. In the control group 31 (51.7%) were male and 29 (48.3%) were females respectively. There is no statistically significant

difference in gender of the participants in both the groups (p = 0.855)

There were 4, 23, 9, 24 cases of left mastoidectomy, left tympanoplasty, right mastoidectomy and right tympanoplasty respectively in benzydamine group. In control group, there were 1, 26, 4, 29 cases of left

mastoidectomy, left tympanoplasty, right mastoidectomy and right tympanoplasty respectively. There was no statistically significant difference between the groups ($p = 0.257$).

In the postoperative period, 12 patients had nausea and vomiting in the benzydamine group as compared to 11 patients in the control group. Local tingling was observed in 6 patients in benzydamine group which was clinically not significant.

Table 2. Satisfaction of patients at 24 hours among the study participants

Time point	Patient's Satisfaction	Intervention group (Benzydamine) N=60 n (%)	Control group (Normal Saline) N =60 n (%)	p value
24 hours	Satisfied	60 (100.0)	52 (86.7)	0.006†
	Not satisfied	0 (0.00)	8 (13.3)	

At 24 hrs after surgery and extubation, all the patients in benzydamine group were satisfied and comfortable as compared to 52 patients in control group.

Discussion

This study showed that preoperative gargling with Benzydamine hydrochloride solution for 30 seconds, five minutes before orotracheal intubation was effective in reducing the incidence and severity of sore throat, cough and hoarseness of voice in the postoperative period without any complications as compared to placebo group in patients undergoing elective middle ear surgeries under general anaesthesia. POST may be caused by pharyngeal, laryngeal, or tracheal irritation and may occur even in the absence of endotracheal intubation [12]. It is difficult to differentiate whether POST is secondary to laryngoscopy alone, or is caused by insertion of an endotracheal tube, or is a combined effect of the two. Numerous pharmacological and non-pharmacological approaches to prevent or minimize the incidence and severity of POST have been tried with conflicting results. Among them benzydamine hydrochloride which possesses pluripotent actions has been proposed as an agent for the prevention of POST. Not much literature is available about the use of benzydamine hydrochloride (BH) gargling on POST. Benzydamine hydrochloride (BH) is a topical NSAID that has analgesic, local anaesthetic, anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial properties with a terminal half-life of approximately 8 ho. Although local drug concentrations are relatively large, the systemic absorption of mouthwash-gargle of benzydamine is relatively low compared to oral doses, this lower absorption should greatly diminish the potential for any systemic drug side effects when BH is administered by gargling. Hence we chose to administer Benzydamine in form of gargle for the intervention group. The contributing factors for POST include sex, age, use of succinylcholine, larger tracheal tubes, cuff design, and intracuff pressures. [13] In our study, no correlation was observed between age, gender, duration of surgery. We had chosen ASA 1 or 2 group of patients for the study who underwent surgeries on middle ear like tympanoplasty and mastoidectomy which lasted less than 4 hrs. They found that at 24 hrs after extubation

incidence and severity of POST and cough were significantly lower in lidocaine group. We studied the effect of benzydamine hydrochloride on postoperative cough. We found that immediately after extubation and at 6 hrs postoperatively no significant difference in incidence when compared to control group. At 2 hrs and 4 hrs after extubation there was significantly decreased incidence in benzydamine group as compared to control group. At 24 hrs after extubation none of the patients had cough in both the groups. The side effects of topical use of benzydamine hydrochloride include local numbness or burning, stinging sensation, nausea or vomiting, cough and hoarseness. We did not observe any statistically significant difference among the intervention group and the control group in side effects. Biro P et al studied the effect of coughing and bucking during extubation on the incidence of POST. They observed that coughing and bucking can increase the incidence and severity. [14] We avoided the frequency of patient coughing and bucking during extubation by gentle oral suctioning and smooth extubation.

Conclusion

Preoperative gargling with benzydamine hydrochloride solution for 30 seconds, five minutes before intubation, reduces the incidence and severity of sore throat in patients who underwent elective middle ear surgery under general anaesthesia with endotracheal in the postoperative period. The incidence and severity of cough and hoarseness were also reduced in the postoperative period.

References

1. Park SH, Han SH, Do SH, Kim JW, Rhee KY, Kim JH. Prophylactic dexamethasone decreases the incidence of sore throat and hoarseness after tracheal extubation with a double-lumen endobronchial tube. *Anesth Analg.* 2008;107 (6): 1814-8.
2. Mokhtar AM, Choy CY. Postoperative sore throat in children: comparison between proseal LMA and classic LMA. *Middle East J Anaesthesiol.* 2013;22(1):65-70.
3. Higgins PP, Chung F, Mezei G. Postoperative sore throat after ambulatory surgery. *Br J Anaesth.* 2002; 88:582-4.

4. Ayoub CM, Ghobashy A, Koch ME, McGrimley L, Pascale V, Qadir S, et al. Widespread application of topical steroids to decrease sore throat, hoarseness, and cough after tracheal intubation. *Anesth Analg*. 1998;87(3):714-6.
5. Stout DM, Bishop MJ, Dwersteg JF, Cullen BF. Correlation of endotracheal tube size with sore throat and hoarseness following general anaesthesia. *Anesthesiology*. 1987;67(3):419-21.
6. Biro P, Seifert B, Pasch T. Complaints of sore throat after tracheal intubation: a prospective evaluation. *Eur J Anaesthesiol*. 2005;22(4):307-11.
7. Hari Kumar S, Saravanan D, Ranganathan S, Sumathi K. Post-operative sore throat—Incidence and contributory factors. *Journal of pharmaceutical and biomedical sciences*. 2013; 26(26):286-92.
8. Koshy E, Curcin V, Bottle A, Sharland M, Saxena S. Sore throat consultations in general practice prior to tonsillectomy among eight hundred and sixty-three children in England: is this in accordance with the SIGN guidelines? *Clin Otolaryngol*. 2013;38(3):266-70.
9. Yadav M, Chalumuru N, Gopinath R. Effect of magnesium sulfate nebulization on the incidence of postoperative sore throat. *J Anaesthesiol Clin Pharmacol*. 2016; 32:168-71.
10. McHardy FE, Chung F. Postoperative sore throat: Cause, prevention and treatment. *Anaesthesia*. 1999;54(5):444-53.
11. Gal TJ. Airway management. In: Miller RD, Fleisher LA, Joshns RA, Savarese JJ, Wiener-Kronish JP, Young WL, eds. *Miller's Anaesthesia*, 6th ed. Philadelphia: Elsevier. 2005; 16177–52.
12. Turnbull RS. Benzylamine Hydrochloride (Tantum) in the management of oral inflammatory conditions. *Journal Can Den Assoc*. 1995; 61(2):127-34.
13. Hu B, Bao R, Wang X, Liu S, Tao T, Xie Q, et al. The size of endotracheal tube and sore throat after surgery: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *PLoS One*. 2013;8:e74467.
14. Vangipuram Raghava Chari, Arnab Paul. Comparative study to analyse the incidence of sore throat, cough, and hoarseness of voice after general anaesthesia with the use of topical benzylamine hydrochloride and 2% lignocaine gel with placebo. *Med J DY Patil Univ*. 2016;9: 61-5.